

**STYLISTIC FUNCTIONS OF EPITHETS IN LITERARY TEXT (ON
THE MATERIAL OF THE NOVEL, “THE PICTURE OF DORIAN GRAY”
BY OSCAR WILDE).**

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Abstract: This article examines the stylistic functions of epithets in Oscar Wilde's novel The Picture of Dorian Gray. The analysis explores how epithets contribute to the creation of vivid imagery, character development, mood establishment, and the reinforcement of philosophical themes.

Key words: stylistics, epithet, function, imagery, characterization, symbolism, contrast.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются стилистические функции эпитетов в романе Оскара Уайльда «Портрет Дориана Грея». В результате исследования выявляют, эпитеты, способствующие созданию ярких образов, развитию персонажей, установлению настроения и усилению философских тем.

Ключевые слова: стилистика, эпитет, функция, образность, характеристика, символика, контраст.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola Oskar Uayldning “Dorian Grey surati” romanidagi epitetlarning stilistik vazifalarini o‘rganadi. Tahlil epitetlarning jonli tasvirlarni yaratishga, xarak-terlarni rivojlantirishga, kayfiyatni o‘rnatishga va falsafiy mavzularni mustahkamlashga qanday yordam berishini o‘rganadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: stilistika, epitet, funksiya, obrazlilik, xarakteristika, simvolizm, kontrast.

Introduction

Stylistic devices serve as powerful tools in literature, enriching texts by evoking emotions, creating vivid imagery, and conveying complex ideas with artistic precision. Among these, the epithet stands out as a significant literary device, characterized by its ability to add depth and color to descriptions, thereby shaping readers' perceptions of characters, settings, and themes. Oscar Wilde's *The Picture of Dorian Gray* offers a fertile ground for examining the stylistic functions of epithets, as the novel is replete with Wilde's ornate language and masterful use of expressive means. The epithets in the text not only reflect the characters' inner worlds but also contribute to the broader themes of aestheticism, morality, and decay. This thesis explores the role of epithets in Wilde's novel, focusing on their stylistic and functional contributions. It examines how Wilde employs this device to create multilayered meanings, enhance the narrative's aesthetic quality, and underscore the moral complexities inherent in the story. By analyzing selected examples from the text, this study aims to demonstrate the epithet's importance in Wilde's literary artistry.

A literary text is a work of written art that conveys ideas, emotions, and stories through imaginative and creative use of language. Unlike non-literary texts, which focus on facts and information, literary texts prioritize artistic expression, often employing stylistic devices, symbolism, and layered meanings to engage readers emotionally and intellectually. Examples include novels, poems, plays, and short stories. According to Culler (1997), "literary texts are distinguished by their ability to generate meaning through a close engagement with language and form, transcending ordinary communication" [4.50]. Wellek and Warren (1949) describe literary texts as "a form of verbal art, marked by the integration of style, content, and structure, which serves both aesthetic and communicative purposes" [8.129].

An epithet is a stylistic device used in literature to describe a person, object, or phenomenon by emphasizing its inherent qualities or characteristics. It often takes the

form of an adjective, adjective phrase, or descriptive noun that conveys additional meaning beyond the literal. Epithets enrich the language, making it more expressive and vivid. Leech and Short (1981) define an epithet as "an adjective or descriptive phrase that conveys a subjective or emotional quality to its referent, thereby enriching the text's expressive power" [6.243]. Abrams and Harpham (2012) state that "epithets are frequently employed in literature to attribute specific qualities to characters, objects, or scenes, creating vivid imagery and aiding thematic development" [1.270].

Key Functions of Epithet

1. **Characterization.** Wilde uses epithets to vividly describe his characters, revealing their traits and moral states. For example: "radiant youth" , "withered cynic". These epithets describe Dorian Gray at the beginning of the novel, emphasizing his beauty and innocence [9.25], capture Lord Henry’s disillusioned perspective on life and his corrupting influence on Dorian [9.48]. Besides, they guide readers' impressions of the characters and their roles in the narrative.

2. **Creating Atmosphere.** Epithets contribute to the novel’s decadent ambiance:

Take "oppressive splendor" as an example, the epithet reflects the grandeur and moral

decay of Dorian’s luxurious surroundings [9.73]. In addition, "haunting music" evokes a

sense of unease and aligns with the novel’s foreboding tone [9. 98].

3. **Thematic Reinforcement.** Wilde’s epithets reinforce the novel’s central themes of beauty, morality, and decay: "eternal charm" signifies Dorian’s obsession with youth and beauty, illustrating the aesthetic philosophy he adopts [9.29]. Another sample, "tainted soul" reflects Dorian’s internal corruption, contrasting with his unchanging physical appearance [9.162].

4. **Symbolic Layering.** Epithets often imbue objects with deeper meaning, symbolizing the moral and aesthetic dilemmas of the story: "poisonous book" refers to the novel that profoundly influences Dorian, symbolizing the corruptive power of

decadent ideas [9.117]. However, "scarlet lips" conveys both sensual allure and moral danger, encapsulating the dual nature of beauty and vice [9. 58].

Conclusion

In conclusion, the stylistic functions of the epithets in “The Picture of Dorian Gray” extend far beyond mere ornamentation. They are essential to the novel’s artistic expression, thematic depth, and moral critique. Wilde’s masterful use of epithets not only enriches the narrative’s sensory appeal but also reinforces its exploration of the dualities inherent in human nature and society. Through this device, Wilde crafts a text that is as complex and layered as its protagonist, leaving an indelible mark on the reader and solidifying the novel’s place as a masterpiece of aesthetic literature.

The List of Used Literature.

1. Abrams, M. H., & Harpham, G. G. (2012). *A Glossary of Literary Terms* (10th ed.). Cengage Learning, pp. 384 .
2. Birch, D. (1989). *Language, Literature and Critical Practice: Ways of Analysing Text*. Routledge, pp. 272.
3. Crystal, D., & Davy, D. (1969). *Investigating English Style*. Longman, pp. 224.
4. Culler, J. (1997). *Literary Theory: A Very Short Introduction*. Oxford University Press, pp. 165.
5. Galperin, I. R. (1977). *Stylistics*. Moscow: Higher School Publishing House, pp. 334.
6. Leech, G., & Short, M. (1981). *Style in Fiction: A Linguistic Introduction to English Fictional Prose*. Longman, pp. 416.
7. Panjiyeva N.N., (2021). Cognitive features of stylistic devices // *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning*. Academia Science Publishing. ISSN:2776-0995. Indonesia, Vol., 2, 2021, - p. 31-34.
8. Wellek, R., & Warren, A. (1949). *Theory of Literature*. Harcourt, Brace & World, Inc. pp. 408.
9. Wilde, O. (1890). *The Picture of Dorian Gray*. Lippincott's Monthly Magazine, pp. 344 (varies slightly by edition).